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THE PLACE AND ROLE OF PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract: By forms of educational organization, we understand the types of training that the teacher conducts with students in a specific period and order. Nowadays, it is common to conduct education in the form of a class-lesson in general education schools. Looking at the history of mankind, the forms of educational organization appeared and developed in accordance with the interests of the social system.

Key words: education, psychology, youth, pedagogue.

Preparing the youth of our Republic, which is on its way to independent development, for a new social environment, educating them in the spirit of the times is one of the urgent and priority tasks of this day. The fate of the reforms implemented in our republic depends on the moral image and personal integrity of the youth. The implementation of these tasks requires full awareness of democratic principles in human relations. The formation of social relations between people in the East is unique and in accordance with the psychology of each nation. This study guide will help to understand the psychological nature of the changes taking place in human spirituality and psyche during the renewal of society. To enrich the spiritual world of young people who are forming before the scientific research, to inculcate the foundations of the national idea in their minds, to educate the sense of patriotism, to think about the past and the great future, to form a sense of pride in it, to form a new way of thinking, to communicate in accordance with the market economy. goals such as ensuring the assimilation of culture are set. For this, the school age, which is considered an important period in the development of a person, and the correct psychological orientation of the school team determine the urgency of the work. By the forms of educational organization, we understand the types of training that the teacher conducts with students in a specific period and order. Nowadays, it is common to conduct education in the form of a class-lesson in general education schools. Looking at the history of mankind, the forms of educational organization appeared and developed in accordance with the interests of the social system.

When studying the child's psyche, the researcher must rely on and follow a number of principles. These principles are as follows: The principle of objectivity requires the researcher not to confuse the interpretation of the data with the connection. For example, if it is said that the child was looking out of the mirror during the lesson, then the information about this specific event is considered to be Ub. But to say that "the child is inattentive" is an interpretation of the phenomenon. The event itself should not be confused with its interpretation. Because even in the above example, the child is looking at the mirror, but he may be paying a lot of attention to the teacher's words.

Please note that preschool is a period of transition for our young children, therefore attention to the child increases at this time. This period is the period of strengthening and development of voluntary attention.

At the end of preschool education, the growth of visual thinking accelerates and the process of developing logical thinking begins. This leads to the formation of the ability to generalize, compare and classify in the child, as well as the ability to determine the main characteristics of the surrounding objects. By the end of the preschool education period, the development and formation of personality, as well as the child's mental state, are related to the development of self-awareness. Children of 6-7 years of age are gradually forming an assessment of their own activities, which depends on understanding how successful their activities are, their peers and how successful they are in evaluating the views of teachers

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and others around them. There are also psychological means of human interaction and communication. When people interact with each other, one of their main goals is to influence each other, i.e. to persuade their ideas, call to action, change attitudes and is to make a good impression. Psychological influence is the ability to influence people's thoughts, feelings and behavior through various means. In social psychology, three main means of psychological influence are distinguished.

1. Verbal influence is the influence we exert through our words and speech. The main tools in this are words. It is known that speech is a conversation, a process of interaction, and its tool is words. Both in monologue speech and dialogic speech, a person wants to influence his partner by finding the most effective words, using all his vocabulary.

2. Paralinguistic influence is the surrounding factors that disturb the speech, strengthen or weaken it. This includes high-pitched or low-pitched speech, articulation, sounds, pauses, stuttering, coughing, tongue movements, exclamations. Depending on this, for example, if our friend promises us something, we will know how sincere he is. We certainly believe that he will say "I will do it!" with an open face and a bold voice.

3. The meaning of non-verbal influence is "without speech". This includes the positions of the interlocutors in relation to each other, positions (close, distant, intimate), gestures, facial expressions, pantomimes, looks, direct feelings of each other, appearance, various signals (noise, smells) coming out of it. All of them enhance the communication process and help the interlocutors to get to know each other better.

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